

Superconducting properties of tungsten meander structures fabricated by focused ion beam technique

Girija Shankar Papanai^{1,2}, Sudhir Husale¹, Anurag Singh¹, Anurag Gupta¹, V N Ojha¹, and R P Aloysius^{1*}

¹CSIR-National Physical Laboratory, New Delhi-110012, India

²Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research, Chennai-600113, India

alosp@nplindia.org 07838350564

Abstract

Focused ion beam (FIB) deposited tungsten is reported to have a superconducting transition temperature of ~ 5 K (1), as it forms an amorphous alloy comprising of W, Ga and C. Here we report the fabrication and superconducting characteristics of meander structure of tungsten deposited by FIB technique. Two such structures were fabricated with varying width ~ 450 nm (sample1) and ~ 300 nm (sample2). The superconducting transition temperature of sample1 is 4.5 K and that of sample2 is 4.3 K, which were measured in the Dilution Refrigerator having a base temperature of 20 mK. While the $R(H)$ characteristics of Sample1 is of a typical type-II superconductor, sample2 shows some anomalies including resistance oscillations, the H_{C2} values of both the structures is estimated to be ~ 9.5 T. The figure given below shows the variation of normalized resistance as a function of temperature along with SEM image of the meander structures.

Keywords- Superconductors, FIB, Dilution Refrigerator, meander structure

References

1. E. S. Sadki et al, App.Phys. Lett.85 (2004) 6206.